

EFFICIENT PARALLEL DESIGN/PLACEMENT OPTIMIZATION METHODOLOGY OF LARGE SMART STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: The title methodology is formulated for optimal sizing of structural members and/or placement of active elements for structural weight minimization and shape control of piezoelectric-type smart structures in a parallel environment. The efficient, stochastic-type Integral Global/Local Optimization algorithm (IGLOA) is first extended to form a discrete design variable (D) version, IGLOA_D, and used to develop optimization procedures to solve this class of mixed integer/discrete/continuous design variable optimization problems. The design variables include both structural sizing (such as cross-sectional area, etc.) and active element placement/design (such as number, location, and/or control gain) variables. Several numerical design/placement optimization examples of 72- and 504-bar piezoelectric-type smart truss structures are presented for demonstration purposes. Excellent computational timing and optimization results have been obtained, indicating that the algorithm/methodology is capable of solving this class of computationally intense, large-size, smart structural optimization problems.

KEYWORDS: optimization method; integer, discrete, and continuous design variables; weight and energy minimization; active element placement; smart structures

INTRODUCTION

An optimal placement problem of active elements for structural shape control with respect to active element number, location, and control gain value is a mixed integer/discrete/continuous design variable (MIDCDV) optimization problem. Solution of this class of mixed design variable problems is particularly computationally intense because one cannot take advantage of gradient (sensitivity derivative) information in the optimization process. Three most widely used (and better) methods for solving MIDCDV problems are the Genetic Algorithms (GAs), Simulated Annealing (SA), and Branch and Bond Method (BBM). Application of these methods (with the most widely used GAs followed by the SA of stochastic-type) in optimal placement optimization problems of active elements or actuators for structural shape or vibration control can be found, among others, in [1-3], respectively. While these methods have been found effective in varying degrees for solving small-to-medium size optimization problems, they are generally not suitable for solving large-scale, MIDCDV-type optimization problems because of the excessive computational time required even in a massively parallel computational environment. Even for engineering optimization problems with continuous design variables (CDVs), some problems exist for the most widely used gradient-based optimization (GBO) methods [4] (such as a tendency to be trapped in a local minima, tendency for inefficiency or for frequently not yielding a convergent solution for large-scale optimization problems, and for less amenability than a stochastic method to a massively parallel computing environment).

Therefore, the author has taken a different unified approach for attacking large-scale engineering design optimization problems of both CDV and MIDCDV-types by formulating and enhancing a powerful, parallel stochastic-type algorithm, Integral Global/Local Optimization algorithm, IGLOA [5], which is a local random search augmented Integral Global Optimization (IGO) algorithm [6]. Application of the algorithm in solving large-scale structural design optimization problems has been made successfully [6]. A comparison study of the IGLOA with a vastly improved version of the widely used, stochastic-type Genetic Algorithms [7] shows that the former outperforms the latter in both computational efficiency and optimal global solution areas [8]. For example, in solving a structural weight minimization problem of an asymmetric 72-bar truss with 72 design variables (cross-sectional areas), the IGLOA was found to be computationally at least two-orders of magnitude more efficient than a significantly improved version of the GAs [7]. Furthermore, the IGLOA was also found to be capable of obtaining the best minimized structural weight result, i.e., 60% smaller than that based on the best improved GA at 100K function evaluations. Thus far, the IGLOA has been formulated mainly for and applied to the CDV optimization problems, although it was also used in an exploratory study of optimal placement problems of active elements for shape control of truss and frame structures [9]. In the present study, formal extension/refinement of the IGLOA algorithm to the MIDCDV case is first made and then applied to the sizing design/active element placement optimization problems of large smart structures. The optimization problems are posed as minimization of objective function of combined structural weight, strain energy, and/or control gain sum with respect to sizing design variables (cross-sectional areas, second moments of inertia, etc.) and/or active element placement/control variables (number, locations, and/or control gains) under a set of design and behavioral constraints. Formulation of the optimization problem is given in Section 2. Solution procedure/ methodology of the optimization problem is formulated in Section 3. Section 4 contains several example problems for demonstration purposes.

FORMULATION OF OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

The design/placement optimization problems for weight minimization and/or shape control of a smart structure with mixed integer/discrete/continuous design variables (MIDCDVs) can be stated as below. Optimization is to be performed for the objective function F such that

$$Z = F(\{X\}) = \sum_{i=1, N_c} X_{Ci} F \rightarrow \text{Minimum} \quad (1a)$$

with respect to design variables $\{X\} = \{X_S|X_G|X_D|X_I|X_C\}$ and subjected to the constraints

$$\{X^L\} \leq \{X\} \leq \{X^U\}$$

$$(\{X_C^L\} = \{0\}, \{X_C^U\} = \{1\}); \sum_{i=1, N_c} X_{Ci} = 1 \quad (1b)$$

$$\{H(\{X\})\} \leq \{0\} \quad (1c)$$

$$\{L(\{X\})\} = \{0\} \quad (1d)$$

where $\{H\}$ and $\{L\}$ are the inequality behavioral and equality side constraint function vectors, respectively; N_C is the number of subobjective functions, F_i ; $\{X_K\}$ of vector lengths N_K with subscripts $K = S, G, D, I,$ and C denoting the partitioned subvectors of continuous cross-sectional sizing variables, continuous control gain variables, discrete active element location variables, integer variables (such as the number of active elements), and objective function coefficient variables ($N_C =$ number of subobjective functions, F_i), respectively; and superscripts L and U stand for "lower" and "upper" bounds, respectively.

Many subclasses of the smart structural optimization problems stated above exist. The following specific subobjective functions and design variables are considered:

- a) Subobjective functions -- $F_1 =$ structural weight (W), $F_2 =$ strain energy (Q) or maximum displacement (U_{max}), and $F_3 =$ control gain sum ($G_{sum}=G_1+G_2+...G_{N_C}$).
- b) Design variables -- i) $\{X_S\} = N_S$ -groups of independent structural element cross-sectional areas ($\{A\}$) with $N_S \leq N_E =$ number of structural elements for the truss structure case and areas ($\{A\}$) or areas and second moments of inertia ($\{X_S\}^T = \{\{A\}^T\{J\}^T\}^T$ with $N_S \leq 2N_E$, where superscript T stands for "transpose" of a vector or matrix) for frame structures; ii) $\{X_G\} =$ control gains ($\{G\}$) of displacement amplifiers); iii) $\{X_D\} = \{X_L\} =$ active element (sensor/actuator) locations, which may be jointly expressed with $\{X_G\}$ by assigning X_{Gi} a zero or nonzero positive value ($\{0\} \ll \{G^L \leq \{G\} \leq \{G^U\}$) according to whether the i -th sensor/actuator pair of a structural element is active ($G_i > 0$) and present ($G_i > 0$) or absent ($G_i = 0$) with $N_G \leq n_p \times N_E$, where $n_p =$ maximum number of distributed sensor/actuator pairs in each structural element; iv) $\{X_I\} =$ number of groups of independent active elements (N_A) with $N_I = 1$; and v) $\{X_C\} =$ coefficient variables of $\{F_i\}$ ($i=1, \dots, N_C \leq 3$). If all of these design variables are present, the total number of design variables is $N_X = N_S + 2N_G + N_A + N_C$, of which the numbers of continuous, discrete, and integer variables are $N_S + N_G + N_C$, N_G , and $N_I (=1)$, respectively.
- c) Constraint functions $\{H\}$ -- i) behavioral variable constraints: displacement-type, $\{H_q\} = \{\{q\} - \{q_{max}\}\}$, stress-type, $\{H_s\} = \{s\} - \{s_{max}\}$, and piezoelectric active element voltage carrying capacity-type, $\{H_v\} = \{v\} - \{v_{max}\}$; ii) design variable inequality constraints as given in Eqn 1b, and iii) equality design variable constraints: unity coefficient design variable sum-type, $L_C = \sum_{i=1, N_C} X_{Ci}$ and constant gain sum (G^*)-type, $L_G = \sum_{i=1, N_A} X_{Gi} - G^*$, if appropriate.

PARALLEL SOLUTION PROCEDURE/METHODOLOGY

IGLO_D Optimization Algorithm (IGLOA_D)

As mentioned in the introductory section, the stochastic-type IGLOA is a local (Koosh) search augmented Integral Global Optimization (IGO) algorithm [5]. It is proposed to extend the algorithm to solve the class of mixed integer/discrete/continuous design variable optimization problem of smart structures as follows:

- Step 1. First specify an initial search region and establish an initial average.
- Step 2. The design variable search regions of integer-type (such as the number of active elements), discrete-type (locations of active elements quantified by those elements

having nonzero gain values), and continuous-type (sizing variables of all structural elements and gain values of active elements) are then sampled at random, and the corresponding objective functions evaluated.

- Step 3. Points at which the objective function are below the current average are added to the list of points, called "good" points. When the length of this list grows above some threshold, the average value of the objective function is computed for points on the list. Points at which the value of the objective function is above this new average are removed from the list.
- Step 4. The new search region is then chosen to be an N_X -dimensional rectangle slightly larger than required to hold all points on the current list of good points, where N_X is the number of design variables, which for the most general case of design/placement optimization problem under consideration is $N_X = N_S + N_G + N_L + N_A + N_C$. For continuous design variables and the integer variable (number of active distributed sensor/actuator pairs), the corresponding subregions can be specified by simply providing upper and lower design variable bounds to each design variable. For the discrete variables of sensor/actuator pair locations, a second (auxiliary) list must be established. This list contains the candidate active sensor/actuator pair IDs, from which N_A -design variables of active distributed sensor/actuator elements will be chosen. The simplest acceptable way is to include all candidate sensor/actuator IDs, as in [9]. In the present improved version of the algorithm, only those active element (or unit) IDs that are associated with those good points on the good point list are included in this second (good active element) list. It should be noted that, while the number of on-list active elements remain constant for the former case, it will shrink for the latter (present) case as the optimization search continues. Now the iteration is ready to begin again.
- Step 5. When many points have been examined but few points have been added to the history list of good points under consideration, one goes to local search mode that is called Local (Koosh) search. In this mode, small neighborhoods of the best points on the current good point list (including the auxiliary list) are searched. This is done only long enough to get enough good points on the list to be able to make meaningful updates to the average and search region. The search is then returned to the top level (IGO) algorithm. Depending on how the neighborhoods are defined for the discrete variables of active element locations in the above local search, different local discrete variable space search subalgorithms can be formulated. One concept of neighborhoods for active element locations are that of the structural elements adjacent to the onlist active elements.
- Step 6. These global/local search steps are repeated until meeting a specified stop criterion, which may be either that the original search region has shrunk to a small fraction value or that the percentage of change of two successive objective function values is below a given small percentage value.

In what follows, the study of the algorithm will be confined to a subalgorithm (IGLOA_D1) in which the discrete/integer variable search portions will be confined to the global (IGO) search mode only, while the local search will be done for the continuous design variable portions only, i.e., the algorithm described in Steps 1-6 minus the integer/discrete variable search portions in Step 5. This is because the full algorithm itself merits a separate in-depth study. We are also

interested in applying the subalgorithm to solve some large-scale design/ placement optimization problems of smart structures in a parallel environment.

Parallel Smart Structural Analysis Procedure

To perform design/placement optimization of smart structures, it is required to perform analysis/reanalysis to obtain structural response quantities appearing in the objective functions and/or constraint conditions. For this, only frame and truss-type smart structures comprised of active, distributed piezoelectric sensor/actuator structural elements and regular (passive) elements will be considered. The governing finite element (FE) equations of equilibrium for such structures with piezoelectric sensor/actuator layers bonded on the four outer faces of host structural element with hollow rectangular cross-section have been derived by the writer in [10]. The element end force ($\{f\}_i$)-displacement $\{u\}_i$ relationships for a typical active i -th element following negative position feedback law between a bi-layered sensor/actuator pair are of the form

$$\{f\}_i = [k]_i \{u\}_i - \{p\}_i \quad ([k]_i = [k_e]_i + [k_p]_i) \quad (2a)$$

where $\{p\}_i$ is the force vector associated with the distributed forces; $[k_e]_i$ and $[k_p]_i$ are the elastic and piezoelectric portions of the i -th element stiffness matrix, $[k]_i$, respectively. Note that $[k_p]_i$ and, thus, $[k]_i$ matrices are generally asymmetric. The former is given by

$$[k_p]_i = [b_a]_i [g]_i [b_s]_i \quad (2b)$$

Here, $[b_a]$ and $[b_s]$ are the (12×4) element actuator force ($\{f_a\}$) and (4×12) sensor signal matrices, respectively, and $[g]$ the (4×4) diagonal element position feedback control gain matrix. The $[b_a]$ and $[b_s]$ (and, thus, $[k_p]$) matrices have been derived by the writer for the hollow beam rectangular cross section case with PVDF piezoelectric sensor/actuator pair layers bonded to the four outer beam surfaces (sectors) [10]. The assembled equations of equilibrium for a frame or truss structure, after using the element end and nodal displacement vector ($\{u\}$)- $\{q\}$ relationships, $\{u\}_i = [B]_i \{q\}$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N_E$), where $[B]_i$ is a $(12 \times N_q)$ Boolean matrix, can be written as

$$[K] \{q\} = \{P\} \quad ([K] = \sum_{i=1, N_E} [B]_i^T [k]_i [B]_i = [K_e] + [K_p], \{P\} = \sum_{i=1, N_E} [B]_i^T \{p\}_i) \quad (3)$$

To obtain relevant smart structural responses, Eqn 3 is first solved for $\{q\}$. The element end displacements $\{u\}_i$ are then also known. The actuator voltages can be obtained from voltage-displacement relations [10]. The stress quantities can be obtained in a typical fashion.

In a multiple-instruction-multiple-data (MIMD) computational environment using a message passing paradigm, such as that of the parallel IBM SP computers or PVM or MPI networked parallel workstation clusters, each processor has sufficient random access memory to solve a sufficiently large-size structural reanalysis problem in design optimization, particularly if the Preconditioned Conjugate Gradient (PCG) method of linear system solution is used to solve a typically sparse FE discretized linear system. Therefore, it is particularly efficient to assign a processor to solve a complete structural response solution of the multiple structural solutions (under randomly generated design variable sets) required for optimization.

Parallel Smart Structural Design/Placement Optimization (PSSDPO) Procedure

Processor Assignment Strategy: In a sequential computational environment, over 95 percent and less than 5 percent of computational time are spent on structural response computations/optimization (objective and constraint) function evaluations and remaining IGLO optimization search operations, respectively. Therefore, the former tasks (response computations/function evaluations) are assigned to parallel slave processors, with each processor performing one set of a complete structural response analysis, an associated constraint treatment operation, and a single objective function calculation. The latter (i.e., IGLO optimization search) task is assigned to a single master processor.

Load Balancing Strategy: In conjunction with the above processor assignment strategy, the following efficient load balancing strategy under a homogeneous or heterogeneous processing environment has been formulated and used. In this strategy, the required number of design variable sets are generated sequentially in the master processor and sent to multiple slave processors one-by-one for structural response function analyses and optimization function evaluations. Immediately after receiving a set of design variable/objective function data from a slave processor, the master processor generates a new design variable vector and sends it to that slave processor to perform new set of analyses/evaluations. This will result in keeping all multiple slave processor busy all the time, thus having faster (or in the homogeneous processor configuration case, less busy) processors yielding a larger number of analysis/evaluation sets.

PSSDPO Computational Procedure: These parallel computational/implementation strategies and structural analysis and IGLOA_D-based optimization procedures forms an efficient PSSDPO computational procedure.

PARALLEL IMPLEMENTATION AND NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

Parallel Implementation of the PSSDPO Computational Procedure

The IGLOA_D1-based subset of the foregoing PSSDPO computational procedure for truss and frame structures has been implemented into the writer's previously developed parallel structural analysis/design optimization code, PSTRAND, as PSTRAND_D1, on the IBM high performance SP2 computer platform and used in the following numerical study of example problems. The following three quantities will be used in measuring computational performance of a structural design optimization algorithm, methodology, and/or procedure: (i) number of function evaluations, N_F , in which one evaluation includes all calculations for relevant structural responses and satisfying constraints required for obtaining one objective function; (ii) accumulated cycles of iteration, N_{cyc} , to obtain convergent structural response solutions via the use of Preconditioned Conjugate Gradient (PCG) Method; and (iii) wall-clock (WC) time. The former two are good measurements for numerical performance evaluation independent of computer machine used (parallel or serial).

Assumptions and Design Parameters Used in the Example Problems

In the following examples, all element cross-sections of the host truss structures (Figure 1) are assumed to be of thin-walled, hollow rectangular-type fabricated from aluminum material, on

outface of it a pair of PVDF PZ layers (each with 0.022 cm thickness) is bonded if the element is of active type. The material properties and design parameters are given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. 72-Bar (n=4) and 504-Bar (n=28) Truss Minimum Weight Design Problems.

Symmetric 72-Bar Truss Optimization Cases

The passive host structure is subjected to two loading sets and is under displacement and stress constraints as given in Figure 1, in which the maximum allowable displacements are $q_{max} = 0.635$ and 0.3175 cm corresponding to the baseline and modified (Mod. 1) optimization design cases, respectively. In the optimization, an equivalent 144-bar truss structural model, comprised of two identical 72-bar trusses subjected to the first and second loading sets, respectively, is used.

Host Structural Weight Minimization Cases. The design variables in this case are the 16 independent groups of cross-sectional areas. The best minimum structural weight of $W_0=172.22$ Kg (= 379.66 lbs.) for the baseline case ($q_{max}= 0.635$ cm = 0.25 in) obtained by previous authors is based on a gradient-based optimization (GBO) algorithm of Sequential Quadratic Programming (SQP). The present IGLOA-based PSSDPO capability yielded the best weight result of $W = 1.0044W_0$ requiring only $N_F = 2755$ function evaluations and $N_{cyc} = 53,212$ accumulated PCG iteration cycles, indicating the effectiveness of the IGLOA-based structural optimization method. The corresponding IGLOA-based best weight result for the Mod. 1 design case ($q_{max} = 0.3175$ cm = 0.125 inch) is found to be $W = 1.96W_0$ and $W_1 = 1.95W_0 = 335.85$ Kg at (N_F, N_{cyc}) pairs of (2698, 52983) and (4388, 86460), respectively, corresponding to the cases of using coarser and finer searches.

Smart Structural Technology-Based Weight Minimization Cases: The Mod. 1 host structural weight minimization problem is to be performed with respect to not only the 16-groups of independent cross-sectional (c.-s.) areas as before, but also to 16 groups each of the active element's locations and control gains and a single integer design variable of a number of active elements with 49 design variables in all. The lower and upper bound pairs for these design variables are: (0.6452, 30.0) cm, (1, 16), (1E+09, 1E+12) V, and (1, 16), respectively. The constraint conditions are, as before, the maximum allowable displacement of 0.3175 cm

and 1757.7 Kg/cm². (More realistically, maximum allowable voltage constraints should also be imposed. Without such constraints, one needs to properly set/choose the allowable range of gain voltage and/or PZ layer thicknesses.) The minimum weight design and computational performance (N_F and N_{cyc}) results obtained in the preceding passive structural design, are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Final Weight Minimization/Active Element Placement and Computational Performance Results for 72-Bar PZ Truss

Bay No.	Areas (cm ²)/Gains (GV) for Intra-Bay truss Member Nos.			
	1-4	5-12	13-16	17-18
1	0.8945/69.023	0.6744/33.510	0.6452/0.000	0.6549/0.000
2	0.8217/133.63	0.6452/39.238	0.6452/0.000	0.6452/0.000
3	0.6452/93.794	0.6452/27.334	0.8233/0.000	0.7309/0.000
4	1.8161/0.000	0.6452/37.812	0.8537/0.000	0.6452/36.296
Optimal results: $N_A = 8$ (46 act. elements); $W = 0.5132W_0 = 88.39$ Kg; $G_{sum} = 2.36E+12$ V; Av. Energy = 2,241.3 Kg-cm; $N_F = 6554$; $N_{cyc} = 179,284$.				

The best minimized weight result is $W_2 = 88.48$ Kg = $0.5132W_0 = 0.263W_1$. Because of the presence of 46 (8 groups) of the optimally placed active elements with optimally designed gain values, the total weight (including those of the optimally designed baseline host structure and additional PZ layers for the active elements) is reduced by nearly 50% while reducing the maximum displacement by 50%. Without such active elements, it requires nearly twice the baseline weight (four times of the smart structural weight) to reduce the maximum displacement of 0.635 cm by 50% to 0.3175 cm.

Smart Structural Energy Function Minimization Case. The baseline structural energy function (work done by external forces) was also minimized with respect to the active element's locations and gain values under a preassigned or optimally obtained number of active elements. Some optimization results are given in Table 2 under different gain sum (G_{sum}) values and number of active element groups (N_A). The weight ratios are seen to be greater than unity because of the additional PZ layer weight due to the presence of active elements.

Table 2. Final Energy Minimization/Active Element Placement Results_a

Case No.	G_{sum} (GV)	N_A	NAE group IDs ^b	W/W ₀	Av. E (kg-cm)	Max. q (cm)	N_F	N_{cyc}
1	2586.	12	3, 7, 8, 11	1.303	1502.	0.2546	3,262	71,883
2		13	3, 4, 7	1.312	2417.	0.4419	2,699	53,806
3		12 ^c	3, 7, 8, 11	1.302	2418.	0.4561	1,901	37,536
4		6 ^c	2, 5, 7, 8, 10, 12, 15, 16	1.149	2553.	0.5656	1,797	36,948

a. Under lower and upper gain value design limits of 1 to 1000 GVs.

b. Non-active element (NAE) group IDs = design area group IDs.

c. These are preassigned number of active elements, while the others (for cases 1-3) are obtained optimally.

For the preassigned cases (3 and 4) of $N_A = 12$ and 6, the final energy values are seen to be slightly and significantly greater than the optimum energy value, as was expected.

Symmetric 504-Bar Truss Optimization Cases (112 Groups of Design C.-S. Areas)

Host (Passive) Structural Weight Minimization Case. The structural configuration, loading set, and design parameters are shown in Figure 1 (with $n = 28$). The maximum allowable displacement now is 6.35 cm (5 inches). The truss is subjected to the first loading set only. The IGLOA-based final best minimized weight for the passive structure case was found to be $W_0 = \sim 3,860$ Kg (8500 lbs. = 5% of the initial average weight) consuming 40 wall-clock minutes on the 24-node NASA AMES SP2 of which approximately 50% of the time was spent on reducing the last 5% of the final weight. This is because (i) the rate of decrease in objective function becomes slower and slower as the average objective function approaches its minimum value and (ii) a stringent computational stopping criterion was used, which required three consecutive decreasing changes in average objective functions under two successive optimization iterations to be less than 0.01%. The number of functions evaluated to get the best optimization results are $\sim 74,000$.

Smart Structural Weight Minimization Case. To further reduce the structural weight, as in the preceding design case, one uses active elements and performs weight minimization/active element placement design with respect to both sizing and active element design variables (c.-s. areas and locations, gains, and/or number of active elements). The weight minimization results are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Optimal Structural Weight/Active Element Placement Design Results for Symmetric 504-Bar Smart Structure Truss ($N_A=20$) on the 16-node MHPCC SP2

Items	W_n/W_0	G_{sum} (V)	Max q (cm)	N_{Fn}	WC (min)
Final results	0.7234	3.152E+13	11.13	$\sim 80,000$	~ 90
20 active elem. group ID nos.	1, 14, 15, 20, 21, 28, 30, 45, 53, 57, 63, 70, 71, 75, 81, 84, 92, 100, 103, 112 (Total number of active elements = 80 in 20 groups)				

The final smart structural weight is seen to be $\sim 72\%$ of the minimized host (passive) structural weight under the same inequality displacement and stress constraint conditions and additional equality gain sum constraint of $3.152E+13$ V. It took $\sim 80K$ function evaluations and ~ 90 minutes of 16 node SP2 wall-clock time to solve this 504-bar smart truss structural optimization problem with 337 design variables. It took $\sim 80K$ function evaluations and ~ 90 minutes of 16 node SP2 wall-clock time to solve this 504-bar smart truss structural optimization problem with 337 design variables.

CONCLUSIONS

The Integral Global/Local algorithm (IGLOA) has been extended as IGLOA_D to solve the mixed integer/discrete/continuous design variable structural sizing/active placement design optimization problems of large smart structures for weight minimization and shape control. An IGLOA_D-based parallel design/placement optimization procedure for frame and truss-type smart structures was then formulated, and its subset (based on IGLOA_D1) was implemented on the IBM SP2 computer platform. Several numerical structural weight and energy minimization examples of plain and smart truss structure-type with 72 and 504 structural elements were presented for demonstration purposes. These study results show that the formulated optimization algorithm and procedure are capable of performing the optimization efficiently and excellently. However, more thorough study of the methodology

is needed, particularly in solving the large-scale/large structural optimization problems, such as the 504-bar truss problem studied here. A comparison study of the methodology with other methods to solve smart structural problems is desirable to further evaluate the parallel IGLOA_D-based methodology.

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